

A Note on the Misspecification of the Random Effects Distribution in the Bayesian Analysis of Basket Trials with Time-to-Event Endpoints

Aaron Springford¹, Emma Mackay¹

¹Cytel, 1 University Ave, Third Floor, Toronto, Ontario, Canada

Abstract

Random effects are usually assumed to follow a normal distribution, except perhaps in frailty models which typically assume a gamma distribution. In some cases, careful consideration of the process under study may lead to these common choices. In other cases, the random effects distribution is chosen for convenience. There is no consensus on whether the misspecification of the random effects distribution leads to poor inference (bias, loss of efficiency) relative to the correct random effects distribution, and it likely depends on the particular situation.

Using statistical simulation, we investigate misspecification of the random effects distribution in a Bayesian hierarchical survival model (BHM), and evaluate the performance of robust alternatives. As our motivating example, we consider data arising from basket trials of mutation-targeted, tumor-agnostic therapies in oncology. Patients in these trials have different types of cancer but share a rare mutation, and their prognosis can vary widely as a function of cancer type. BHMs have been suggested to "borrow" information across cancer types in these trials due to the small number of patients.

Key Words: Bayesian, survival analysis, misspecification, basket trials, oncology.

1. Survival analysis of basket trials

A challenge for modern therapies in oncology which target a specific but rare mutation is that there are few patients available for recruitment into clinical trials. These targeted therapies may be considered for treatment of patients with diverse cancer types based on the idea that the presence of the targeted mutation will result in improved outcomes under treatment, regardless of the cancer type. Assessment of tumor-agnostic therapies may be investigated in a basket trial, in which patients are recruited based on the presence of the mutation rather than the type of cancer. There has been an increased use of basket trials in recent years, the majority being early phase trials in oncology (Park et al, 2019). Often, basket trials will not include a control arm, and standardized response (based on tumor shrinkage) will be the measure of efficacy – rather than overall survival (OS) or progression-free survival (PFS) – due to differences in prognosis as a function of cancer type. However, response to treatment does not necessarily lead to improved outcomes from a patient's perspective, and delaying negative outcomes such as disease progression or death remains an important consideration when evaluating these treatments.

When estimating the efficacy of the treatment in a basket trial, pooled efficacy estimates may differ depending on the number of patients with each type of cancer in the basket. Conversely, each type of cancer may be analyzed separately if there are enough patients included to achieve adequate statistical power. However, in many cases, the targeted mutation is uncommon and patients with some types of cancer will be few. To improve precision when estimating efficacy, it has been proposed to use a Bayesian hierarchical model (BHM)(Murphy et al, 2021). Taking response to treatment as the measure of efficacy, the proportion of responders for each type of cancer is given a parameter, and these are assumed to follow a normal distribution whose mean and variance are

likewise parameterised and given vague prior distributions. This kind of hierarchical model has been thoroughly studied and results in partial pooling of the probability of response among cancer types, with shrinkage towards the overall average probability of response for each cancer type.

Less well-studied are time-to-event models of endpoints such as OS and PFS (Mackay et al, 2022). As in the case of the standardized response endpoint, we can define a BHM which models the time-to-event so that the parameter of the survival likelihood is assumed to follow a normal distribution with unknown mean and variance. However, given the differing prognoses among cancer types, it is not clear whether such a model is flexible enough to characterise the anticipated differences in the survival parameter.

The BHM survival models we consider are of the following form:

$$P(y|\lambda, \delta) = \prod_i (\lambda_{k(i)} e^{-\lambda_{k(i)} y_i})^{1-\delta_i} (e^{-\lambda_{k(i)} y_i})^{\delta_i}$$

$$\log(\lambda_k) \sim f_\lambda(\theta)$$

$$\theta \sim f_\theta$$

so that the likelihood corresponds to an exponential survival distribution with parameter λ , the event times are y , and the right-censoring indicator is δ . The rate parameters $\lambda_{k(i)}$ for individual i belonging to group k follow a distribution f_λ with parameter θ . The family of this distribution is our primary focus – we are interested in the consequences of different choices for f_λ and particularly cases in which the distribution is misspecified (doesn't match the data-generating model).

2. Simulation design

Using simulation, we investigated the impact of misspecification of the f_λ distribution for a hierarchical Bayesian time-to-event analysis of data which would typically arise from basket trials in oncology. We simulated data for a set of ten cancer types in which the parameters $\lambda_{1,\dots,10}$ of the survival likelihood followed a mixture normal distribution with two components (Figure 1). One component of the mixture represented seven cancers with typically longer survival:

$$\log \lambda_k \sim N(\mu = -1, \sigma = 0.3); k \in \{1,2, \dots,7\}.$$

The other component of the mixture represented three aggressive cancers with typically shorter survival:

$$\log \lambda_k \sim N(\mu = 0.5, \sigma = 0.5); k \in \{8,9,10\}.$$

Figure 1: Mixture distribution used to simulate basket trial survival data.

In each simulation, 100 patients were allocated to the ten cancer types with equal probability. For patients $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, event times $T_i \sim \text{Exp}(\lambda_i)$ and right-censoring times $C_i \sim \text{Exp}(-2)$ were simulated, and observed times $T_i^* = \min(T_i, C_i)$ were calculated. We simulated 100 data sets with 100 patients.

Next, we performed Bayesian inference for each of the 100 simulated data sets using the BHM structure but one of four distributions for f_λ :

1. A mixture normal prior, with $\theta = \{\mu_1, \mu_2, \sigma_1, \sigma_2\}$ and hyperpriors: $\mu \sim t_3(s = 2.5)$ and $\sigma \sim \text{gamma}(a = 2, b = 1/4)$. This is the correct family which generated the simulated data.
2. A normal prior, with $\theta = \{\mu, \sigma\}$ and hyperpriors: $\mu \sim t_3(s = 2.5)$ and $\sigma \sim \text{half-}t_3(s = 2.5)$. This represents a default choice which is recommended for modelling response rates.
3. A non-central t-distribution prior, with three degrees of freedom, $\theta = \{\mu, s\}$ and hyperpriors: $\mu \sim t_3(s_\mu = 2.5)$ and $s \sim \text{half-}t_3(s_s = 2.5)$. This represents a robust alternative to the normal distribution with heavier tails.
4. A non-central Cauchy prior, with $\theta = \{\mu, \sigma\}$ and hyperpriors: $\mu \sim t_3(s = 2.5)$ and $\sigma \sim \text{half-}t_3(s = 2.5)$. This choice has even more heavy tails than the t-distribution.

We are interested in assessing the effect of a misspecified prior distribution on the inferred time-to-event across different cancer types in the simulated basket trial. It is possible, for example, that the normal prior results in adequate inference and that the parameters of the survival model are estimated as well as for the alternatives, even if the true underlying distribution is non-normal. We anticipate that the mixture normal prior should be able to out-perform the normal prior if the true underlying distribution is mixture normal, but it is also possible that this model may be too flexible if there are very few patients for some cancer types. The t-distribution and Cauchy priors represent possible robust middle-ground priors that may strike the right balance between the normal and the true distribution of random effects.

Inference was performed using the Stan language (version 2.26.1) and R (version 4.2.3) and rstan (version 2.26.22) (R Core Team, Stan Development Team). An example of the results from a single simulation are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Example of single simulation showing Kaplan-Meier survival curves overlaid with mean posterior survival curves using the mixture distribution for the $\log \lambda_k$. Cancer type labeled as histology.

3. Results

We summarise the simulation-estimation results across the set of 100 simulations separately for each component of the mixture distribution used to generate the data. We are chiefly interested in inferring the value of λ , since knowledge of this parameter would be most valuable for decision-making in this context. We examine three characteristics of the effect of model misspecification:

1. Bias, defined as the average difference between the mean of the posterior for λ and the true value, across the one hundred simulations.
2. Mean-squared-error (MSE), defined as the average squared difference between the mean of the posterior for λ and the true value, across the one hundred simulations, and the square root of MSE (RMSE).
3. The proportion of 95 percent credible intervals which contain the true value for λ , across the one hundred simulations.

Comparing the four HBMs, the model with the mixture normal distribution prior had the smallest bias for the two groups and the normal prior had the largest; the t-distribution and Cauchy were in between (Figure 3). In general, there was shrinkage of the parameter estimates. In terms of RMSE, the normal distribution had the best performance in spite of having the largest bias (Figure 4), suggesting that in the current data-limited situation, this model may be inducing more shrinkage toward the mean $\log \lambda$ and improving the RMSE. When it came to coverage of credible intervals, the mixture normal model had the best coverage, and was the best at characterising the uncertainty particularly for the smaller set of cancer types with shorter time-to-event (Figure 5).

Figure 3: Bias by cancer type group across the set of one hundred simulations. Group 1 are the seven cancer types with typically longer survival times, and group 2 are the three cancer types with typically shorter survival times.

Figure 4: Root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) by cancer type group across the set of one hundred simulations. Group 1 are the seven cancer types with typically longer survival times, and group 2 are the three cancer types with typically shorter survival times.

Figure 5: Coverage of 95 percent credible intervals by cancer type group across the set of one hundred simulations. Group 1 are the seven cancer types with typically longer survival times, and group 2 are the three cancer types with typically shorter survival times. The dashed line represents the intended coverage of the interval.

4. Discussion

When analyzing basket trials in tumor-agnostic therapies for health technology assessment, BHMs have some key advantages. BHMs can be used for inference even if some cancer types have very few patients because of the inclusion of a group-level random effects distribution. Additionally, a probabilistic framework can be useful for formal decision-making which involves cost/benefit analysis and formal risk assessment of different treatment options. Finally, information could be included in priors if available to improve inference in these typically data-poor situations (Mackay and Springford, 2023).

In survival models, parameters of the survival function may follow a non-symmetric or even multi-modal distribution across cancer types. We wanted to investigate whether the typical choice of a normal distribution would be suitable in this context, particularly given that an arguably more realistic/flexible distribution may be difficult to implement and highly uncertain given the context

of limited sample size. Anticipating that the normal distribution may not be able to capture the heterogeneity among cancer types, we also investigated the t-distribution and Cauchy as robust alternatives to the normal. In our simulated set of basket trials, we found that the true model (a mixture normal) had the smallest bias when estimating cancer type-specific survival, the normal model had the most bias, and the robust alternatives were indeed able to reduce bias compared to the normal model. However, our results also underscore that in this data-limited situation, the normal model appears to induce shrinkage of the survival parameters towards the overall mean, reducing the RMSE. Thus, if the objective is to produce more reliable assessment of the survival parameters overall, at the expense of bias in individual assessments, then the normal model may be a suitable choice.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by Cytel, Inc. The authors are employed by Cytel and do not have any competing interests to declare.

References

- Mackay E, Springford A, Nagamuthu C, Dron L. A Bayesian Hierarchical Modelling Approach for Indirect Comparison of Response Outcomes in Histology-Independent Therapies [abstract]. In: ISPOR Europe 2022 Conference; Nov. 2022; Vienna, Austria. <https://www.ispor.org/heor-resources/presentations-database/presentation/euro2022-3565/121665>.
- Mackay EK, Springford A. Evaluating treatments in rare indications warrants a Bayesian approach. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 2023;14.
- Murphy P, Claxton L, Hodgson R, Glynn D, Beresford L, Walton M, Llewellyn A, Palmer S, Dias S. Exploring heterogeneity in histology-independent technologies and the implications for cost-effectiveness. *Medical Decision Making*. 2021 Feb;41(2):165-78.
- Park JJ, Siden E, Zoratti MJ, Dron L, Harari O, Singer J, Lester RT, Thorlund K, Mills EJ. Systematic review of basket trials, umbrella trials, and platform trials: a landscape analysis of master protocols. *Trials*. 2019 Dec;20(1):1-0.
- R Core Team. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. 2023. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Stan Development Team. RStan: the R interface to Stan. R package version 2.26.22. <https://mc-stan.org/>.